

[Biomarker Analytical Laboratories](#)

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Title: SOP for automated on-line liquid-liquid extraction (LLE) workflow for anthropogenic profiling of human plasma samples via GC-HRMS

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Summary

In this SOP we show the automated on-line liquid-liquid extraction (LLE) of human plasma samples. Prepared extracts are analysed via gas chromatography (GC) with full-scan high-resolution mass spectrometry (GC-HRMS). Presented method is used for profiling of environmental contaminants in human plasma samples.

Sample preparation is often a crucial and at the same time time-consuming part of the analysis. We show a modern robotic sample preparation approach (via TriPlus RSH autosampler) yielding to sequential sample preparation with on-line GC-HRMS analysis. This SOP describes a complete method includes robotic autosampler setup using TriPlus RSH Sampling Workflow Editor 1.4.0.4 software, as well as GC and HRMS method description.

Preparation

Safety information

All work should be conducted in fume hood.

- 2,2,4-Trimethylpentane (isooctane): Danger – highly flammable, skin irritation, may cause drowsiness or dizziness.
- Formic acid: Danger – flammable liquid and vapor, harmful if swallowed, causes several skins burns and eye damage, toxic if inhaled.
- Nonane: Danger – flammable liquid and vapor, fatal when swallowed and enters airways, causes skin irritation, may cause drowsiness or dizziness, very toxic to aquatic life with long lasting effect.
- Toluene: Danger – highly flammable liquid and vapor, may cause drowsiness or dizziness, suspected of damaging the unborn child, may cause damage to organs through prolonged exposure, harmful to aquatic life.

- Acetone: Danger – highly flammable liquid and vapor, causes serious eye irritation, may cause drowsiness or dizziness.
- D10-Acenaphthene: very toxic to aquatic life with long lasting effect.
- D4-Nonylphenol: Danger - harmful if swallowed, causes severe skin burns and eye damage, Suspected of damaging fertility or the unborn child, very toxic to aquatic life with long lasting effects.
- D14-para-Terphenyl: Causes serious eye irritation, may cause long lasting harmful effects to aquatic life.

Equipment

- 200 μ L pipettes

TriPlus RSH Autosampler equipment

- Extended Rail Triplus RSH Base Configuration
- Automatic Tool Change Station
- Solvent Station with solvent bottle 100 mL (6)
- Standard Wash Station (5)
- Fast Wash station (8)
- 3 x Liquid syringe tool for 57 mm syringe needle (9)
- 2 x 100 μ L Fixed Needle Gas-Tight Syringe 23s Gauge 57 mm Length (9)
- 10 μ L Fixed Needle Gas-Tight Syringe 23S Gauge 57 mm Length (9)
- Centrifuge Combi with RCF up to 2000 x g at 4800 rpm (7)
- Vortexer (3)
- Temperature Controlled Drawer (1)
- Trayholder with adapter for 2 mL vials (2)

Software

- Chromeleon 7.2.10 for data acquisition
- TriPlus RSH Sampling Workflow Editor 1.4.0.4

Consumables & glassware

- 2 mL screw cap glass autosampler vials with magnetic caps (PAL System Screw Cap 2 CV, designed for the PA Autosampler) with PTFE septa
- Labels for 2 mL vials
- Vial, ambr screw 2ml; Agilent Technologies; cat. 5190-9063

Reagents

- 2,2,4-Trimethylpentane (isooctane) GC grade $\geq 99.5\%$ purity
- Formic acid (FA) 98-100% purity
- Nonane anhydrous $\geq 99.5\%$ purity
- Toluene anhydrous $\geq 99.8\%$ purity
- Acetone for pesticide residue analysis $> 99.8\%$ purity
- Milli-Q water

Standards

- D10-Acenaphthene; Sigma Aldrich; cat. 451819
- D4-Nonylphenol; Sigma-Aldrich; cat. 614343
- D12-Perylene; Sigma-Aldrich; cat. 490490
- D14-para-Terphenyl; Sigma-Aldrich; cat. 364630
- D7-Cholesterol; Avanti; cat. 700041P
- C7-C40 Saturated Alkanes Standard; Supelco; cat. 49452-U
- Fully resolved native mono-deca PCB mixture unlabelled; Cambridge Isotope Laboratories; cat. CIL-EC-5434

Procedure

NOTE: Plasma samples store at -80°C ; work on ice; use clean baked vials

NOTE: Use Milli-Q water as Procedural blank

1. Label vials
2. Move plasma samples from -80°C freezer, let them thaw at a room temperature and pipette 100 μL to autosampler glass vial and close the vial with magnetic cap; then place vials to temperature-controlled drawer (standby temperature set to 5°C)

3. Fill 100 mL bottle with FA Pos1 (Solvent 1)
4. Fill 100 mL bottle with isooctane Pos2 (Solvent 1)
5. Fill 20 ml bottle with nonane (Standard Wash 1, Wash Index 1)
6. Fill 20 mL bottle with toluene (Standard Wash 1, Wash Index 2)
7. Fill 20 mL bottle with acetone (Standard Wash 1, Wash Index 3)
8. Fill 20 ml bottle with isooctane (Standard Wash 1, Wash Index 4)
9. Fill bottle Wash1 with 5% methanol
10. Fill bottle Wash2 with isooctane
11. Fill 2 mL glass vial with 1500 μ L of labelled standard mix in isooctane

NOTE: Final concentration of labelled standard mix in sample: D4-Nonylphenol c=1000 ng/mL; D10-Acenaphthene c=1000 ng/mL; D12-Perylene c=100 ng/mL; D14-para-Terphenyl c=100 ng/mL; D7-Cholesterol c=1000 ng/mL

NOTE: To prevent contamination, use for all stock solutions aluminium foil instead of septa

TO MEASURE DATA VIA GC ORBITRAP

GC-MS method setup

GC Inlets (TRACE 1300/1310)

Liner: Wool PTV, Restek, cat 21117-213.5

O-ring; Thermo Scientific; cat. 29001318

Front Inlet Options	Use this inlet ✓	
Temperature Settings	Enable temperature control ✓	
	Temperature	70°C
Inlet Parameters	Operation mode	Splitless
	Split flow control ✓	
	Split flow	10 ml/min
	Splitless time	1 min
	Purge flow control ✓	
	Purge flow	5 ml/min
	Constant setup purge ✓	
PTV Ramp Settings	Vacuum compensation ✓	
	Injection	0.05 min
	Transfer	8.5°C/s

		330°C
		1.00 min
	Cleaning	14.5°C/s
		350°C
		10 min
		50 ml/min
Enable clean phase✓		
Front Flow/Pressure Options	Constant flow	1.2 mL/min

GC Oven Settings (Trace 1300/1310)

Prep Run Timeout	25 min		
Oven equilibration time	0.5 min		
Ready delay	0.0 min		
Mode	Ramped temperature		
Retention time [min]	Rate [°C/min]	Target value [°C]	Hold time [min]
0.000	Run		
0.500	0.00	80	0.5
4.000	40.00	200	0.5
6.000	40.00	260	0.5
13.473	55.00	330	6.2
13.473	StopRun		

GC Aux Heaters (TRACE1300/1310)

Heater1	Enable ✓	
	Temperature	280°C
Heater2	Enable✓	
	Temperature	280°C

GC (TRACE1300/1310)

Column: Rxi-5Sil MS; 0.25 um, 0.25 mmID; 15m length; Restek; cat. 13620 (use 15 m column)

Post-column: Rxi Guard Column 0.25 mmID; 5 m length; Restek; cat. 10029 (install only 2 m)

Pre-column: Rxi Guard Column; 0.53 mmID, 5 m length; Restek; cat. 10054 (install only 2 m)

Column nut, Self Tightening; Agilent Technologies; cat. 5190-5233

To inlet: Compact Ferrules 0.8 mm (graphite); Restek; cat. 20285

To MS: Ferules 0.4 mm; 85% Vespel/15% Graphite; Restek;
cat. 27071

Kit + connectors, MicroUnion Siltite; 0.25-0.53 ID; Restek;
cat. 23887

Kit + connectors, MicroUnion Siltite, 0.25-0.25 ID; Restek; cat. 23885

BackColumn	Validate column configuration✓	
	Length	15.00 m
	Diameter	0.25 mm
	Film thickness	0.25 µm

MSDevice (Orbitrap Exploris GC 240)

Global Parameters

Application Mode	Default		
Method Duration (min)	13.47		
Internal Mass Calibration	Off		
Ion Source Properties	Filament Power Table	Time (min)	State
	1	0	Off
	2	1.8	On
	Use Ion Source Settings from Tune	/	
	Ion Source Temp	280	
	Ionization Mode	EI	
	Calibration Gas	Static	
	Calibration Gas Level	Off	
	Filament	Static	
	Emission Current	50	
	Electron Energy	70	
	Electron Lens	15	
	C -Trap Offset	Use From Tune	
	Optics	Use From Tune	

Scan Parameters

Full Scan	Full Scan Properties	Orbitrap Resolution	60 000
		Scan Range (m/z)	70-700
		AGC Target	Custom
		Normalized AGC Target (%)	100
		Maximum Injection Time Mode	Auto
		Microscans	1
		Data Type	Profile

		Polarity	Positive
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System

Run Time	13.47 min
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Autosampler settings

1. Set Temperature	Status Message	Set Temperature	
	Module	DrawerTempCtrl 1	
	Temperature	5°C	
	Tolerance	0.4 K	
	Wait For Temperature	False	
2. Use Tool	Status Message	Use Tool	
		Tool	LS1
3. Transport Vial	Status Message	Transport Vial	
	sampleRack	%sampleRack%	
	sampleIndex	%sampleIndex%	
	Destination	Tray1 (Trayholder 1)	
	Destination Index	1	
4. Clean Syringe	Status Message	Clean Syringe	
	Wash Source	Fast Wash 1	5% methanol
	Wash Index	1	
	Wash Cycles	2	
	Wash Volume	70 %	
	Fill Speed	7 µL/s	
	Wash Source Penetration Depth	25 mm	
	Dispense Speed	100 µL/s	
5. Get Volume	Status Message	Get Volume	
	Source	Pos1 (Solvent 1)	formic acid (FA)
	Source Index	1	
	Volume	25 µL	
	Use Bottom Sense	Off	
	Source Penetration Depth	45 mm	
	Filling Strokes Counts	2	
	Filling Strokes Volume	10 µL	
	Fill Speed	2 µL/s	
	Dispense Speed	100 µL/s	
	Front Air Gap	0 µL	
	Overfill Rate	5 %	

	Aspirate Delay	1 s	
	Pressure Compensation	No	
	Pressure Compensation Penetration Depth	12 mm	
6. Dispense Liq. Into Vial	Status Message	Dispense Liq. Into Vial	
	Sample Rack	%sampleRack%	
	Sample Index	%sampleIndex%	
	Volume	25 µL	
	Destination Penetration Depth	31 mm	
	Dispense Speed	100 µL/s	
	Pressure Compensation	No	
7. Use Tool	Status Message	Use Tool	
	Tool	LS3	
8. Clean Syringe	Status Message	Clean Syringe	
	Wash Source	Fast Wash 1	isooctane
	Wash Index	2	
	Wash Cycles	2	
	Wash Volume	70 %	
	Fill Speed	7 µL/s	
	Wash Source Penetration Depth	25 mm	
	Dispense Speed	100 µL/s	
9. Get Volume	Status Message	Get Volume	
	Source	Pos2 (Solvent 1)	
	Source Index	1	
	Volume	100 µL	
	Use Bottom Sense	Off	
	Source Penetration Depth	45 mm	
	Filling Strokes Counts	2	
	Filling Strokes Volume	10 µL	
	Fill Speed	2 µL/s	
	Dispense Speed	100 µL/s	
	Front Air Gap	0 µL	
	Overfill Rate	5 %	
	Aspirate Delay	1 s	
	Pressure Compensation	No	
10. Dispense Liq. Into Vial	Status Message	Dispense Liq. Into Vial	
	Sample Rack	%sampleRack%	
	Sample Index	%sampleIndex%	
	Volume	100 µL	
	Destination Penetration Depth	31 mm	
	Dispense Speed	100 µL/s	

	Pressure Compensation	No	
11. Get Liquid From Vial	Status Message	Get Liquid FromVial	
	Source	Tray5 (DrawerTempCtrl 1)	
	Source Index	9;18;27;36;45;54;63;72;81	NOTE: design samples in Trayholder
	Volume	100 µL	
	Use Bottom Sense	On	
	Height from Bottom	1 mm	
	Filling Strokes Counts	2	
	Filling Strokes Volume	20 µL	
	Fill Speed	2 µL/s	
	Dispense Speed	100 µL/s	
	Front Air Gap	0 µL	
	Overfill Rate	5 %	
	Aspirate Delay	1 s	
	Pressure Compensation	No	
12. Dispense Liq. Into Vial	Status Message	Dispense Liq. Into Vial	
	Sample Rack	Tray 1 (Trayholder 1)	
	Sample Index	1	
	Volume	100 µL	
	Destination Penetration Depth	31 mm	
	Dispense Speed	100 µL/s	
	Pressure Compensation	No	
13. Vortex Vial	Status Message	Vortex Vial	
	Vortex Mixer	Vortex 1	
	Source	Tray 1 (Trayholder1)	
	Source Index	1	
	Vortexing Time	180 s	
	Vortexing Speed	1200 rpm	
14. Transport Vial	Status Message	Transport Vial	
	sampleRack	%sampleRack%	
	sampleIndex	1	
	Destination	Centrifuge 1	
	Destination Index	6	
15. Centrifuge Vial	Status Message	Centrifuge Vial	
	centrifuge	Centrifuge 1	
	Use Speed Value	True	
	Speed	4800	
	Wait For Constant Condition	True	
	Centrifuge State	On	
16. Wait	Status Message	Wait	

	Time	180 s	
17. Operate Centrifuge Cover	Status Message	Operate Centrifuge Cover	
	Centrifuge	Centrifuge 1	
	Cover Position	Open	
	Transport Vial Home	Status Message	Transport Vial Home
18. Transport Vial Home	Status Message	Transport Vial Home	
19. Use Tool	Status Message	Use Tool	
	Tool	LS2	
20. Wait Overlap on Tray	Status Message	Wait Overlap on Tray	
	Incubation Time	90 s	
	Sample Rack	%sampleRack%	
21. Use Tool	Status Message	Use Tool	
	Tool	LS2	
22. Wait For Sync Signal (GC)	Status Message	Wait For Sync Signal (GC)	
	GC	GC1	
23. Clean Syringe	Status Message	Clean Syringe	
	Wash Source	Standard Wash 1	
	Wash Index	4	
	Wash Cycles	4	
	Wash Volume	70	
	Fill Speed	5 µL/s	
	Wash Source Penetration Depth	42 mm	
	Dispense Speed	100 µL/s	
24. Get Liquid From Vial	Status Message	Get Liquid From Vial	
	Source	%sampleRack%	
	Source Index	%sampleIndex%	
	Volume	6 µL	
	Use Bottom Sense	On	
	Height From Bottom	2.5 mm	
	Filling Strokes Count	0	
	Filling Strokes Volume	0 µL	
	Fill Speed	0.3 µL/s	
	Dispense Speed	20 µL/s	
	Front Air Gap	0 µL	
	Overfill Rate	5 %	
	Aspirate Delay	10 s	
	Pressure Compensation	No	
25. Inject Sample GC Overlap	Status Message	Inject Sample GC Overlap	
	Injector	Ptv	
	GC	GC1	

	Analysis Time	810 s	
	Injection Volume	6 μ L	
	Injection Penetration Depth	35 mm	
	Injection Penetration Speed	40 mm/s	
	Injection Speed	100 μ L/s	
	Pre-inject delay	5 s	
	Post-inject delay	3 s	
	Injection Signal Mode	PlungerUp	
26. Clean Syringe	Status Message	Clean Syringe	
	Wash Source	Standard Wash 1	
	Wash Index	1	
	Wash Cycles 2	4	
	Wash Volume	70 %	
	Fill Speed	15 μ L/s	
	Wash Source Penetration Depth	42 mm	
	Dispense Speed	100 μ L/s	
27. Clean Syringe	Status Message	Clean Syringe	
	Wash Source	Standard Wash 1	
	Wash Index	2	
	Wash Cycles 2	4	
	Wash Volume	70 %	
	Fill Speed	15 μ L/s	
	Wash Source Penetration Depth	42 mm	
	Dispense Speed	100 μ L/s	
28. Clean Syringe	Status Message	Clean Syringe	
	Wash Source	Standard Wash 1	
	Wash Index	3	
	Wash Cycles 2	4	
	Wash Volume	70 %	
	Fill Speed	15 μ L/s	
	Wash Source Penetration Depth	42 mm	
	Dispense Speed	100 μ L/s	

NOTE: During automatic sample preparation, it is necessary to wash/sonicate the syringe before/after analysis (mainly the 10 μ L syringe which is used to inject 6 μ L of the final extract into the GC). This syringe is prone to clogging/partial clogging

Figure 1. Visualization of on-line liquid-liquid extraction (LLE) sample preparation using overlapping. Final time of overall analysis is 23 min/sample. Blue color: sample preparation (use 100 μL of sample; pipette 25 μL of formic acid; pipette 200 μL of isooctane containing D4-Nonylphenol; D10-Acetonaphthene; D12-Perylene; D14-para-Terphehyl; D7-Cholesterol; vortex 3 min at 1200 rpm; vortex 3 min at 1200 rpm; centrifuge 3 min at 4800 rpm; Pipette 6 μL of supernatant). Yellow color: GC run; red and green color: waiting and injection.

Tray layout

- Sample ~ 42
- Procedural blank ~ 4
- External long-term QC ~ 6
- Labelled standard mix ~ 11
- Instrument blank ~ 5
- Alkane mix ~ 2
- NIST SRMs ~ 3x2 (NIST 1950, NIST 1957, NIST 1958)
- PCB mix ~ 2

Figure 2. Example of sample layout in Trayholder 1 and Trayholder 2.

Annex 1

TriPlusRSH Configuration

Figure 3. The modules installed on TriPlusRSH used for on-line liquid-liquid extraction (LLE) sample preparation: Temperature Controlled Drawer (1); Trayholder with adapter for 2mL vials (2); Vortexer (3); GC1 (4); Standard Wash station (5); Solvent Station (6); Centrifuge (7); Fast Wash Station (8); ATC Station (9); ATC station

Application

Version 1.4.0.4

Support Key 62KH-BREC

Robot

Robot Type Robotic Tool Change – RTC

Product Version 2.5.57.2

Edition Thermo

Tools

LS2 (9)

Syringe Type SYT365D0271

NdlGuide Type Magn2mL

Volume 10 μ L

LS3 (9)

Syringe Type SYT365H2141

Ndl Guide Type Magn2mL

Volume 100 μ L

LS1 (9)

Syringe Type SYT365H2141

Ndl Guide Type Magn2mL

Volume 100 μ L

Modules

Vortexer: vortexing with 1 positions for 2 mL **(3)**

Centrifuge (7)

GC1 (4)

Ready GCReady1

Injected Injected1

Prepare none

Ptv (4)

ATC Station 1 (9)

ATC Station 2 (9)

GCReady1

Source TTLIn2

Injected1

Destination SWOut2

Solvent Station: containing 2x200 mL vials **(6)**

Temperature Controlled Drawer: 2x 54 positions tray **(1)**

Drawer 1

Slot1

Rack Type VT54

Rack Item 2-CV Magnetic

Slot2

Rack Type VT54

Rack Item 2-CV Magnetic

Trayholder with adapter for 2mL vials (2)

Slot1

Rack Type VT54

Rack Item 2-CV Magnetic

Fast Wash Station (8)

Standard Wash Station: 5x 10 mL vials (5)

Annex 2

The settings of Autosampler's modules used for this method are listed below:

Note: Other modules can be added to the ATC also other modules are installed to the autosampler

LS1

- Location: Slot 2
- Ndl Guide Type: Magn2mL
- Instrument Length: 122.300 mm
- Length: 135.0 mm
- Syringe Type: SYT365H2141

LS2

- Location: RobotArmLeft
- Ndl Guide Type: Magn2mL
- Instrument Length: 122.300 mm
- Length: 135.0 mm
- Syringe Type: SYT365D0271

LS3

- Location: Slot 3
- Ndl Guide Type: Magn2mL
- Instrument Length: 122.300 mm
- Length: 135.0 mm
- Syringe Type: SYT365H2141

Vortexer 1

- Pos2 Vial Type: None
- Actual Position 0.23 deg

DrawerTempCtrl 1

- Drawer 1
- Actual Temp: 4.9 °C
- Max Temperature: 40.0 °C
- Min Temperature: 4.0 °C
- Stdbby Temp control: on
- Stdbby Temperature: 4.0 °C
- Temp Setpoint: 5.0 °C
- Close Current: 500 mA

- Close Speed: 15 %
- Drawer Sensors: Activated
- FanSpeed: 100 %
- Open Current: 400 mA
- Open Speed: 15%
- PeltierTemperature: -1.6 °C
- Strip Distance X: 15.0 mm
- Temp Offset: 0 d °C

Thayholder 1

- Slot 1
- Cap Type: MagnetCap
- Rack Item: 2-CV Magnetic
- Tray Type: VT54

Large Solvent 1

- Pos 1 > Max needle Penetration Depth: 45.000 mm
 - > Actual Volume: 0 µL
 - > Def Ndl Penetr Depth: 40.000mm
 - > Depenetration Speed: 100 mm/s
 - > Diameter: 73.0 mm
 - > Height: 55.0 mm
 - > Penetration Speed: 40 mm/s
 - > Vial Type: 100SR
 - > Volume: 100.0 mL
 - > Z Tolerance: 5.0 mm
- Pos 2 > Max needle Penetration Depth: 45.000 mm
 - > Actual Volume: 0 µL
 - > Def Ndl Penetr Depth: 40.000mm
 - > Depenetration Speed: 100 mm/s
 - > Diameter: 73.0 mm
 - > Height: 55.0 mm
 - > Penetration Speed: 40 mm/s
 - > Vial Type: 100SR
 - > Volume: 100.0 mL
 - > Z Tolerance: 5.0 mm

Standard Wash 1

- Pos 1 > Max needle Penetration Depth: 46.000 mm
 - > Actual Volume: 0 µL
 - > Def Ndl Penetr Depth: 42.000mm
 - > Depenetration Speed: 100 mm/s
 - > Diameter: 22.0 mm
 - > Height: 49.0 mm

- > Penetration Speed: 40 mm/s
- > Vial Type: 10SR
- > Volume: 10.0 mL
- > Z Tolerance: 5.0 mm

- Pos 2 > Max needle Penetration Depth: 46.000 mm
 - > Actual Volume: 0 μ L
 - > Def Ndl Penetr Depth: 42.000mm
 - > Depenetration Speed: 100 mm/s
 - > Diameter: 22.0 mm
 - > Height: 49.0 mm
 - > Penetration Speed: 40 mm/s
 - > Vial Type: 10SR
 - > Volume: 10.0 mL
 - > Z Tolerance: 5.0 mm

- Pos 3 > Max needle Penetration Depth: 46.000 mm
 - > Actual Volume: 0 μ L
 - > Def Ndl Penetr Depth: 42.000mm
 - > Depenetration Speed: 100 mm/s
 - > Diameter: 22.0 mm
 - > Height: 49.0 mm
 - > Penetration Speed: 40 mm/s
 - > Vial Type: 10SR
 - > Volume: 10.0 mL
 - > Z Tolerance: 5.0 mm

- Pos 4 > Max needle Penetration Depth: 46.000 mm
 - > Actual Volume: 0 μ L
 - > Def Ndl Penetr Depth: 42.000mm
 - > Depenetration Speed: 100 mm/s
 - > Diameter: 22.0 mm
 - > Height: 49.0 mm
 - > Penetration Speed: 40 mm/s
 - > Vial Type: 10SR
 - > Volume: 10.0 mL
 - > Z Tolerance: 5.0 mm

- Waste > Max Ndl Penetr Depth: 46.000 mm
 - > Def Ndl Penetr Depth: 20.000 mm
 - > Depenetration Speed: 100 mm/s
 - > Diameter: 22.0 mm
 - > Height: 49.0 mm

- > Penetration Speed: 40 mm/s
- > Vial Type: Waste Vial
- > Volume: 10.0 mL
- > Z Tolerance: 5.0 mm

Fast Solvent Wash

- MaxFlowRate: 60 μ L/s
- PostRinseLiner: 1
- PreRinseLiner: 0
- Def Ndl Penetr De: 25.000 mm
- Depenetration Sp: 100 mm/s
- Max Ndl Penetr D: 78.000 mm
- Penetration Spee: 40 mm/s
- Z Tolerance: 5.0 mm

Centrifuge 1

- Board
- Drive
 - >Actual Speed: 0 rpm
 - >Actual Position: 45.09 deg
- Actual g-Force: 0
- Actual Rotor Team: 24.6°C
- Actual Speed: 0 rpm
- Auto Stop: 3.0 min

PTV

- Def Ndl Penetr Depth: 35.000 mm
- Max Ndl Penetr Depth: 100.0 mm
- Min Ndl Penetr Depth: 18.0 mm
- Position Tolerance: 4.00 mm
- Z Tolerance: 20.0 mm

RobotArmLeft

- NdlGd motor 1 > Actual Position: -3 μ m
- Plunger motor 1 > Actual Position: 25 μ m
 - > Check Plunger :
- Tool control 1 > LS5 > Location: RobotArmLeft
 - > Ndl Guide Type: Magn2mL
 - > Instrument Length: 122.300 mm
 - > Length: 135.0 mm
 - > Syringe Type: SYT365F2141
 - > NdlGuide Coupling: 8708
 - > Plg. Coupling Count: 8708
 - > Tool Coupling Count: 8708

- X axis motor 1 > Actual Position: 259.998 μm
> Total Axis Length: 1.208 m
- Y axis motor 1 > Actual Position: 0 μm
- Z axis motor 1 > Actual Position: 0 μm
- Acceleration Factor: 10 %
- Default strategy: parallel
- DefaultWaste: none
- Homing Strategy: Default

ATC Station 1

- Slot 1 > LS3 > Location: Slot 1
> Ndl Guide Type: Magn2mL
> Instrument Length: 122.300 mm
> Length: 135.0 mm
> Syringe Type: SYT365H02141
> ParkSlotIndex: 1
> ToolPresent:
> Fiber Protection:
- Slot 2 > LS1 > Location: Slot 2
> Ndl Guide Type: Magn2mL
> Instrument Length: 122.300 mm
> Length: 135.0 mm
> Syringe Type: SYT365H2141
> ParkSlotIndex: 2
> ToolPresent:
> Fiber Protection:
- Slot 3 > ParkSlotIndex: 3
> ToolPresent:
> Fiber Protection:
- ToolEepromAccess:

Input Output 1

- Immediate > Signal On:
> Debounce Time: 0 ms
- OptoIn1 > Signal On:
> Debounce Time: 0 ms
> Low Active:
- PWMOut: > Signal On:
> OutputVoltage: 0 mV
- ResetButton: > Signal On:
> Debounce Time: 0 ms
- Simulated: > Signal On:
> Trigger Event: None
> Waiting Time: 60.0 s

- Software In > Signal On:
- Software Out: > Signal On:
- SWOut1 > Signal On:
 - > Low Active:
- SWOut2: > Signal On:
 - > Low Active:
- TTLIn1 > Signal On:
 - > Debounce Time: 0 ms
 - > Low Active:
- TTLIn2 Signal On:
 - > Debounce Time: 0 ms
 - > Low Active:
- TTLIn3 Signal On:
 - > Debounce Time: 0 ms
 - > Low Active:
- TTLOut1 > Signal On:
 - > Low Active:
- TTLOut2 > Signal On:
 - > Low Active:
- TTLOut3 > Signal On:
 - > Low Active:
- Beep Volume: 4

GC1

- Cryo Trap: None
- Fake Inj Delay: 15000 ms
- Injected: Start
- Prepare: None
- Ready: Gcready

GCReady

- Signal On:
- BlockingTime: 0 ms
- Source: TTLIn1

Start

- Signal On:
- Destination: SWOut1
- DestinationAux: None
- PulseDuration: 300 ms